

The Indian Economic Journal

JOURNAL OF THE INDIAN ECONOMIC ASSOCIATION

Special Issue, December 2018

**PROSPECT OF
ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT GOALS**

The Indian Economic Journal

Editor

Anil Kumar Thakur

Associates Editors

Budhen Kr. Saikia

Balkant Sharma

The Journal, an organ of the Indian Economic Association aims at promoting scientific studies in Economic Theory, Indian Economic Policies, Energy and Water Resources, Human Resource Development, Monetary Economics, International Trade and Finance, Industrial Economics, Poverty and Unemployment and related topics of current interest.

Editor

Dr. Anil Kumar Thakur

General Secretary and Treasurer, IEA

Secretariat Colony, Road No. 3,

House No. B/6, Kankarbagh,

Patna-800 020, Bihar (India)

Phone : 0612-2354084,

Mobile : 09431017096

email : anilkumarthakur.iea@gmail.com

Published by

THE INDIAN ECONOMIC ASSOCIATION

13. Gender Equity Educational Resource and Sustainable Development R. VADIVELU	115
14. A Comparative Study on Correlation between Growth and Status of Sustainable Development Goal 6 – Access to Drinking Water and Sanitation in Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa (BRICS) during 2008 to 2015 M. SUDHA AND K. MANJUSREE NAIDU	124
15. Climate Change Environment Degradation and Sustainable Development: Major Issues and Challenges in South Asia VADRANAM SURESH	134
16. Ecotourism as a Measure of Sustainable Development: Lessons to Learn From Bhutan VATSALA SHARMA	144
17. Financial Inclusion – A Prospect of Achieving Sustainable Development Goals PRATIMA GUPTA AND MANUKANT SHASTRI	149
18. Gender Disparity in Literacy: District Level Analysis of Chhattisgarh State RANU AGRAWAL, RAVINDRA BRAHME AND AMARKANT PANDEY	156
19. Gender Inequality in Education and Economic Conditions in India C. SIVAKKOLUNDU	162
20. Growth and Performance of Tourism in India with Special Reference to Rajasthan REKHA AND DEV KARAN	170
21. Challenges of Epidemic Non-Communicable Diseases and Cardio Vascular Diseases In Modern Era K.V. SONA, V. Vaithianathan AND A.SUGIRTHA RANI	182
22. Millennium Development Goals and Role on Health in India K. PRABHU AND C. DHANDAPANI	189
23. Gender Inequality in Higher Education in India POONAM KUMARI	195
24. Health Economics – Some Issues C.K. GOMATHI AND S.N. SUKUMAR	203
25. Population Growth and Population Policy in India and Tamil Nadu T. RAGHU AND C.K. GOMATHI	212
26. Intellectual Property Rights and Climate Change Principles for Innovation and Access to Tribes for Economic Development DUVVURI V.N. PRADEEP	221
27. Sustainable Urban Mobility: Challenges, Initiatives and Planning K. VELMURUGAN AND C. SIVAKKOLUNDU	230
28. In Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals: A Study with Special Reference to Goal 1 & 2 from Indian Perspective RAGHVENDRA KR SINGH AND CHANDRA PRAKASH AZAD	236

Millennium Development Goals and Role on Health in India

K. Prabhu & C. Dhandapani

INTRODUCTION

The Millennium Development Goals (MDG) was originated from the Millennium Declaration adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations in September 2000. The MDGs helped in bringing out a much needed focus and pressure on basic development issues, which in turn led the governments at national and sub-national levels to do better planning and implement more intensive policies and programmes.

OBJECTIVES

Objectives of MDGs

- Eradication Extreme Poverty and Hunger
- Achieve Universal Primary Education
- Promote Gender Equality and Empower Women
- Reduce Child Mortality
- Improve Maternal Health
- Combat HIV/AIDS, Malaria and TB
- Ensure Environmental Sustainability
- Develop Global Partnership for Development

This paper Focus on the fourth goal of the Reduce the Child Mortality Rate under 5 per 1000 live births. Secondly focus on the fifth goal of the Improve Maternal Health Status. Improving the maternal and child health and their survival are central to the achievement of national health goals under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) as well as the Millennium Development Goals (MDG) 4 and 5.

MDGs Role on Child Health in India

Under-Five Mortality Rate

The under- five mortality rate (U5MR) is the probability (expressed as a rate per 1,000 live births) of a child born in a specified year dying before reaching the age of the five if subject yo current age-specific mortality rates. Majority of the under five deaths

are neonatal deaths which are mainly due to complications and infections happened during birth. In addition to this, the U5MR is sensitive to as wide variety of drivers such as the nutritional status of mothers, level of immunization, available of child and maternal care services, economic conditions in the family, etc.

The U5MR for rural areas is higher than that of urban areas. In 2015, the rural U5MR was 48 whereas the urban U5MR was at 28. The U5MR among females was higher than that of males at all India level (female: 40, male: 40) as well as in rural (female: 50, male: 46) and urban areas (female: 31, male: 36).

As per the SRS results, the U5MR showed a table both in rural and urban areas also decreasing over the years.

2009		2011		2013		2015	
Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
71	41	61	35	55	29	48	28

Source: sample Registration System, office of Registration General of India

Infant Mortality Rate (IMR)

The Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) is the number of death in children under 1 year of age per 1000 live births. The IMR is a very sensitive and important indicator of health as its movements are indicative of the health condition of the population. High neo - natal (less than 29 days of birth) mortality still continues to be a significant contributor to the infant mortality rate in India. In 2015, at national level, 67.8% of the total infant deaths were neo - natal deaths. At national level, the neo - natal mortality rate is 25 and ranges from 15 in urban areas to 29 in rural areas. Among the bigger States, neo - natal mortality ranges from 35 in Odisha to 6 in Kerala. In India, IMR was estimated at 80 per 1,000 live births in 1990. As per SRS 2015, the IMR is at 37 vis -a -vis the target of 27 infant deaths per 1000 live births by 2015. The recent results from SRS shows that, IMR has further declined to 34 in 2016.

In India, significant decline in IMR has been observed both in rural and urban areas over years. However, IMR in the rural areas continues to be at a much higher level than the urban IMR. Although the rural - urban gap in IMR is slowly decreasing, the latest data show that even in 2016 the rural - urban gap in IMR is significant (rural IMR: 38, urban IMR: 23).

During 1990 to 2015, female IMR has declined from 81 to 39 infant deaths per 1000 live births and the decline in male IMR is from 78 to 35 infant deaths per 1000 live births. Further decline has been reported by SRS 2016 (Male IMR: 33, Female IMR: 36). However, the female -male gap in IMR is still persisting.

Infant Mortality Rate by sex - India

Years	Male	Female
1990	78	81
2003	57	64
2006	56	59
2009	49	52
2011	43	46
2013	39	42
2015	35	39
2016	33	36

Source: Sample Registration System, Office of Registrar General of India

Proportion of one year old children immunized against measles

Proportion of 1-year-old children immunized against measles is the percentage of children under one year of age who have received at least one dose of measles vaccine. The indicator provides a measure of the coverage and quality of the child health-care system in the country with the assumption that its level of coverage is likely to represent coverage by other antigens like BCG, DPT, and polio as well, as these are given before the antigen of measles could be given. Besides, among these vaccine-preventable diseases of childhood, measles is the leading cause of child mortality. In order to achieve the prescribed MDG target for reducing child mortality, it is desirable to achieve 100% coverage of one year old children immunized against measles. The NFHS - 4 (2015- 16), showed that, at all India level, 81.1% of children under 12-23 months have received measles vaccine and thus India is lagging in the task of achieving universal coverage of one year old children immunized against measles. However, there is substantial improvement in the coverage of one year old children immunized against measles as the level was at 42% in 1992-93.

IMPORTANT PROGRAMMES AND POLICIES

National Policy on Children 2013

India is home to the largest child population in the world. Declaring its children as the nation's "supremely important asset" in the National Policy for Children, 1974, the Government of India reiterated its commitment to secure the rights of its children by ratifying related international conventions and treaties. The National Charter for Children, 2003 adopted on 9th February 2004, underlined the intent to secure for every child, its inherent right to be a child and enjoy a healthy and happy childhood, to address the root causes that negate the healthy growth and development of children, and to awaken the conscience of the community in the wider societal context to protect children from all forms of abuse, while strengthening the family, society and the Nation.

National Policy on Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE)

The Ministry of Women and Child Development has formulated the National Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) policy and the same has been notified in October 2013. The policy lays down the way forward for a comprehensive approach towards ensuring a sound foundation for survival, growth and development of child with focus on care and early learning of every child. It recognizes the synergistic and interdependent relationship between the health, nutrition, psycho-social and emotional needs of the child.

The Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) Scheme

The Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) Scheme is one of the flagship programmes of the Government of India and represents one of the world's largest and unique programmes for early childhood care and development. It is the foremost symbol of the country's commitment to its children and nursing mothers, as a response to the challenge of providing re-school non-formal education on one hand and breaking the vicious

cycle of malnutrition, morbidity, reduced learning capacity and mortality on the other. The beneficiaries under the Scheme are children in the age group of 0-6 years, pregnant women and lactating mothers.

Objectives of the Scheme:

- To improve the nutritional and health status of children in the age-group 0-6 years;
- To lay the foundation for proper psychological, physical and social development of the child
- To reduce the incidence of mortality, morbidity, malnutrition and school dropout
- To achieve effective co-ordination of policy and implementation amongst the various departments to promote child development and
- To enhance the capability of the mother to look after the normal health and nutritional needs of the child through proper nutrition and health education.

National Health Mission:

The child health programme under the National Health Mission (NHM) comprehensively integrates interventions that improve child survival and addresses factors contributing to infant and under-five mortality. It is now well recognized that child survival cannot be addressed in isolation as it is intricately linked to the health of the mother, which is further determined by her health and development as an adolescent. Therefore, the concept of 'Continuum of Care', that emphasizes on care during critical life stages in order to improve child survival, is being followed under the national programme.

MDGS ROLE ON MATERNAL HEALTH IN INDIA

Maternal Mortality Ratio

The Maternal Mortality Ratio is the number of women who die from any cause related to or aggravated by pregnancy or its management (excluding accidental or incidental causes) during pregnancy and childbirth or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, per 100,000 live births. Such deaths are affected by various factors, including general health status, education and services during pregnancy and childbirth. Most maternal deaths are avoidable, as the health-care solutions to prevent or manage complications are well known. Improving access to ante natal care in pregnancy, skilled care during childbirth, and care and support in the weeks after childbirth will reduce maternal deaths significantly. India, pregnancy related deaths of women have declined over the years. The number of maternal deaths per year has come down from approximately 1,00,000 deaths (1991-2001) to 44,000 deaths in 2012-2013. Though, more than 50% reduction has registered in the approximate number of maternal deaths in the last two decades, the present status shows that, even now, 120 women die of causes associated with pregnancy, in a day, in India.

Approximate number of Maternal Deaths/years

Years	Deaths
1999-2001	100000
2001-2003	80000
2004-2006	67000
2007-2009	56000
2010-2012	47000
2012-2013	44000

Source: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare

The maternal deaths being a rare event require prohibitively large sample size to provide robust estimates. In order to enhance the SRS sample size, the MMR estimates are derived by pooling 3years data to yield reliable estimates of MMR. The first Report on maternal mortality in India (1997-2003) – trends, causes and Risk Factors was released in October, 2006 and the latest estimates are available for the period 2012-2013.

The MDG 5 stipulates that the MMR level be reduced by three fourths between 1990 and 2015. In 1990 the estimated MMR was 437 per 1,00,000 live births. In order to meet the MDG target, the MMR should be reduced to 109 per 1,00,000 live births by 2015. As per the latest ORGI estimates, the MMR status at all India level is at 167 in 2011-13.

Important Programmes and policies

- Promotion of institutional deliveries through Janani Suraksha Yojana: For bringing pregnant women to health facilities for ensuring safe delivery and emergency obstetric care, Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY), a demand promotion scheme was launched in April 2005. In the last three years, 282. 23 lakhs mothers benefitted with an expenditure of Rs. 4623.34 crores.
- Building on the success of JSY Scheme the Government of India launched Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakaram (JSSK) on 1st June, 2011. The initiative entitles all pregnant women delivering in public health institutions to absolutely free and no expense delivery, including caesarean section. The entitlements include free drugs and consumables, free diagnostics, free diet during stay for normal delivery and Csection and free blood whenever required. This initiative also provides for free transport from home to institution, between facilities in case of a referral and drop back home. Similar entitlements were put in place for all sick newborns accessing public health institutions for treatment till 30 days after birth. In 2013, the scheme was expanded to cover complications during ante-natal and post-natal period and also sick infants up to 1 year of age. In 2016-17, 92% of pregnant women received free drugs, 80% free diagnostics, 63% free diet, 70% free home to facility transport while 64% received free drop back home after delivery.
- Recently the 'Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan' guidelines have been disseminated to the States with the objective of a special ANC checkup to all pregnant women by a private doctor on 9th of every month. The objective is to detect any risk factor in the pregnant women with its timely management and birth planning for a safe delivery. Approximately 12,200 and more facilities are providing PMSMA services in

the country. About 4200 volunteers have registered themselves for offering the services and more than 70 lakh ANC checkups have been done till July 2017.

- Antenatal, Intranatal and Postnatal care including Iron and Folic Acid supplementation to pregnant & lactating women for prevention and treatment of anaemia: After the first trimester of pregnancy, every pregnant woman during ANC is also given iron and folic acid (IFA) tablets for six months, after the first trimester of pregnancy and six months post-partum. Pregnant women, who are found to be clinically anaemic, are given double the dose of IFA. During pregnancy, intravenous Iron sucrose therapy is recommended for treatment of severe anaemia. To tackle the problem of anaemia due to malaria particularly in pregnant women and children, Long Lasting Insecticide Nets (LLINs) and Insecticide Treated Bed Nets (ITBNs) are being distributed in endemic areas.
- The process of Maternal Death Review (MDR) has been institutionalized across the country both at facilities and the community level in order to identify not only the medical causes but also some of the socio-economic cultural determinants and the gaps in the system which contribute to the delays causing maternal deaths. This is with the objective of taking corrective action at appropriate levels and improving the quality of obstetric care. MDR is being implemented across the country both at facilities and in the community.

CONCLUSION

The fourth Millennium Development Goal aims to reduce mortality among children under five by two-thirds. India's Under Five Mortality (U5MR) declined from 125 per 1,000 live births in 1990 to 49 per 1,000 live births in 2013. The MDG target is of 42 per 1000, which suggests that India is moderately on track, largely due to the sharp decline in recent years.

Child survival in India needs sharper focus. This includes better managing neonatal and childhood illnesses and improving child survival, particularly among vulnerable communities. Survival risk remains a key challenge for the disadvantaged who have little access to reproductive and child health services. Major states in the heartland of India are likely to fall significantly short of these targets. IMR is lowest in Kerala (12) and highest for Madhya Pradesh (54). The key to significant progress in reducing U5MR and infant mortality rates rests with reducing neonatal deaths, that is, infant deaths that occur within a year of birth at a fast pace.

References

- Millennium Development Goals - final Country Report of India. 2017. (www.mospi.gov.in).
- Millennium Development Goals India country Report- 2015. (www.mospi.gov.in).
- Millennium Development Goals India Country Report 2014.
- National Family Health Survey-4 (2015-16).
- Human Development Report, 2016.
- A strategic approach to Reproductive, Maternal, Newborn, Child, and Adolescent Health (RMNCH+A), in India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt of India, January 2013.
- Health in 2015: from MDGs to SDGs (2015) www.who.in
- WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study (MGRS) (2006)
- United Nations Millennium Development Goals (2015) www.un.org
- Economic Survey Report (2017-18)

The Indian Economic Journal

REGISTERED WITH THE REGISTRAR
OF NEWSPAPER FOR INDIA
RNI Regn. No. 46913/87

Supported by :

NABARD
Mumbai

Indian Economic
Association Trust
for Research &
Development

ISSN 0019-4662

